

THE IMPORTANCE OF FEATURE FILMS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *This article is written about the importance of feature films in improving the effectiveness of English language learning and teaching, the appropriate use of modern technologies, and the teacher's self-research, sense of responsibility, innovation in the lessons, making the lesson interesting.*

Keywords: *feature film, innovation, technology, efficiency, specialization, information and communication, telecommunication.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ФИЛЬМОВ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В данной статье написано о важности художественных фильмов в повышении эффективности изучения и преподавания английского языка, целесообразном использовании современных технологий, а также о самоисследовании учителя, чувстве ответственности, новаторстве на уроках, делании урока интересным. .*

Ключевые слова: *художественный фильм, инновации, технологии, эффективность, специализация, информация и связь, телекоммуникации.*

INTRODUCTION

With the advent of modern technology, the tradition of teaching English has changed significantly. Today, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. Several English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will definitely increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. One of these methods is teaching English using feature films. There are several distinct advantages to this type of training. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward.

Modern teaching methods are gradually replacing traditional teaching. Today, many new programs and shows that help to teach English are regularly broadcasted on television.

It should also be noted that in order to increase the effectiveness of teaching today, new methods of teaching through feature films using new modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of feature film and multimedia had the opportunity to develop four skills and learn through interesting materials both by sight and hearing. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it.

Of course, the use of modern technologies of computer, radio, CD, DVD in any foreign language lessons will further advance the educational process and allow the young generation to learn foreign languages faster.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The fact that some teachers do not know how to use feature films and do not use them during English classes, causes the students to be somewhat bored. It is for this reason that in

order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of feature films and at least multimedia tools during the lesson will further ensure the increase of the interest of the learner. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective.

On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts consisting of complex words to elementary school students or show them through multimedia and computers, when we present teaching materials with very simple texts to middle and high class or group learners, the learners' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they don't master the lessons.

DISCUSSION

This, in turn, can lead to a drop in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students. So, it follows that the main task is not only to use feature films during the lesson, but also to be able to use them in their place and to ensure that the use of feature films serves to increase the student's knowledge. According to the requirements of the current CEFR, i.e. International European Education Standards, there are four: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) learning to write, read, listen, and speak in English is effective from art films during classes and appropriate using is important.

For example, there are rules for playing feature films in listening comprehension classes. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the listening material and be able to analyze it without difficulty. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to prepare the environment for the presentation of the feature film, in which the audience ensures a calm environment, and the teacher pays attention to the quality of the feature film being played and the sound amplifiers work well, and before and after the feature film is broadcast. The exercises to be performed should be ready and students should be provided with handouts. After all the requirements are met, the teacher can start playing the feature film to the students. The broadcast is done at least twice and is subscribed otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and not be able to do the exercises correctly after listening to the feature film.

It is also a very effective way to show and discuss art films and videos to students using multimedia in the course of teaching using art films in speaking and listening learning. It is possible to use the vocabulary familiar to the learners, to explain the words if new and complex words are involved, and after completing the exercises related to the new words, it is possible to show art films.

In order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of watching for everyone, and checking that the loudspeakers are working. Before showing the feature film, the students should discuss the topic of the feature film to be shown, conduct a question and answer session, and then release the feature film after making sure that the students are really interested in the topic. After the feature film is finished, the teacher should be interested in the students' thoughts about the feature film, and perform exercises. When these stages are properly implemented, these lessons will definitely contribute to the growth of students' interests and knowledge.

CONCLUSION

It follows that the role of feature films in enriching our lessons, increasing the effectiveness of English language teaching, and being able to interest students and enrich their

knowledge is incomparable. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

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